

FIBROUS DYSPLASIA OF THE MANDIBLE – CASE REPORT**Dorina Stan,***MD, PhD.,**Braila County Emergency Clinical Hospital***Pusica Zainea,***MD, PhD.,**“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania***Alexandra Toma,***MD, PhD.,**“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania***D.F. Voicu***MD, PhD., Associated Profesor,**“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania***Abstract**

Fibrous dysplasia is a benign bone disorder, characterized by replacement of normal bone, with fibro-osseous tissue. Mandibular involvement is rare, but may cause functional and aesthetic problems.

The reported case is of a 23-year-old female, presented with progressive facial asymmetry and chewing difficulties. Clinical examination showed a firm, painless swelling, of the left mandible. Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) revealed a “ground glass” expansion, without cortical destruction. Histology confirmed monostotic fibrous dysplasia.

Conservative surgery with bone contouring improved facial symmetry and function.

Mandibular fibrous dysplasia requires tailored treatment, with conservative surgery, effective in symptomatic cases.

Keywords: fibrous dysplasia, mandible, oro-maxillofacial surgery

Introduction

Fibrous dysplasia is a benign skeletal lesion, characterized by the replacement of normal bone tissue with immature, disorganized fibro-osseous tissue. It is considered a developmental anomaly, determined by somatic mutations in the GNAS-1 gene, which lead to abnormal proliferation of mesenchymal cells.

Depending on the distribution, fibrous dysplasia can be:

- monostotic – affects a single bone (common form);
- polyostotic – involves several bones, sometimes included in McCune-Albright syndrome.

McCune-Albright syndrome is a complex, rare genetic disorder, caused by a somatic mutation in the GNAS gene, affecting bone, skin, and the endocrine system. Common symptoms include, besides polyostotic fibrous dysplasia of the bones, light brown “café-au-lait” spots on the skin, and various endocrine problems, like precocious puberty, hyperthyroidism, and growth hormone excess - acromegaly). The condition is mosaic, meaning the mutation is not present in every cell, leading to a variable and unique constellation of symptoms in each patient.

In simple fibrous dysplasia, at the craniofacial level, the mandible and maxilla are the bones frequently affected, with manifestations ranging from simple radiographic changes to obvious facial deformities.

The specialized literature describes craniofacial fibrous dysplasia as a distinct clinical entity, with frequent onset in childhood or adolescence and slowly

progressive evolution, until skeletal maturity. The classic radiological appearance “ground glass”, sometimes with mixed litho- and radiolucent areas.

The histological picture shows a fibrous stroma, containing irregular trabeculae of immature bone, without obvious osteoblastic edges.

The treatment is eclectic: asymptomatic lesions can only be monitored, and surgical intervention (bone contouring or resection) is indicated just in cases with aesthetic deformity, functional impairment or complications.

Case report

23-year-old female, without major pathological history.

Reason for presentation: progressive facial asymmetry and difficulty in mastication, occurring for approximately five years.

Clinical examination:

- firm, painless swelling, located at the level of the left mandible body;
- intact oral mucosa, without inflammatory signs;
- modified occlusion, with discrete mandibular deviation

Imaging examination - cone beam computed tomography (CBCT):

- bone expansion with heterogeneous appearance, “ground glass” density;
- diffuse contours, without cortical lysis or periosteal reaction;
- integration of adjacent teeth, without mobility (fig. 1)

Fig. 1

Histopathological examination (fig. 2):
 - fibro-osseous tissue with irregular trabeculae of immature bone (appearance of “chinese letters”);

- dense fibrous stroma;
- absence of osteoblastic edges.

Fig. 2

Final diagnosis: Mandibular monostotic fibrous dysplasia.

Differential diagnosis with:

- Periapical cemento-osseous dysplasias;
- Osteofibrous osteoma;
- Cherubism (rare genetic disorder that causes a protrusion in the lower part of the face);
- Low-grade osteosarcoma (especially for aggressive forms).

Treatment:

In the presented case, conservative surgery (bone contouring and aesthetic remodeling) was chosen, considering the visible deformity and functional impact. The postoperative evolution was favorable, with improvement of facial symmetry and restoration of masticatory function. The patient is monitored periodically by clinical examination and imaging.

Discussion

The present case illustrates the monostotic form (mandible) of fibrous dysplasia, diagnosed in a young patient, with typical evolution: onset in adolescence, slow progression and aesthetic manifestation.

As previously stated, the therapeutic strategy must be individualized:

- clinical and imaging monitoring – for stable cases, without aesthetic or functional impact;
- conservative surgery – to correct deformities and restore function;
- Segmental resection – for severe or recurrent cases.

Radiotherapy is totally contraindicated, as there is a risk of malignant transformation of the lesion.

Conclusions

- Mandibular fibrous dysplasia is a rare, slowly evolving pathology with significant impact on facial aesthetics and masticatory function.
- Correct diagnosis requires clinical-radiological correlation and histopathological confirmation.
- Management must be individualized, with conservative surgery being the optimal solution for symptomatic cases.
- Long-term postoperative monitoring is essential to detect recurrences or complications.

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